

Developing an integrated model to manage chronic lower back pain: Sharing data from the REACH initiative

Researchers from the REACH initiative are making data from multiple clinical trials available through the Vivli repository

The UCSF Dept. of Orthopaedic Surgery received funding as part of the NIH HEAL program to establish the Core Center for Patient-centric, Mechanistic Phenotyping in Chronic Low Back Pain, or REACH. REACH is a member of the Back Pain Consortium ([BACPAC](#)) Research Program, a “translational, patient-centered effort to address the need for effective, non-addictive, and personalized therapies for chronic low back pain.” Its research focus includes Phase 2 clinical trials focused on developing and delivering an integrated model of chronic lower back pain.

Dataset(s) shared: See [Vivli data repository](#) (sign-in required)

Vivli worked with the research team to organize and upload trial data from three related studies to Vivli: one umbrella project—REACH, the chronic low back pain research center—and two observational cohorts under that umbrella, called COMEBACK and Back Home. Kaitlin Yee coordinated the process between the UCSF research team and Vivli, and provided feedback on the data sharing process.

Kaitlin Yee, Research Coordinator, UCSF

Key research information:

- The goal of this study was to develop an objective, accurate, and efficient deep-learning-based method for calculating biomarkers of cartilage endplate health measured using ultra-short echo time magnetic resonance imaging (UTE MRI)
- Data from 83 participants established that trained deep learning models enable accurate, automated segmentations which address limitations associated with manual methods. Such techniques could be used to elucidate the role of CEP composition in disc degeneration etiology and guide emerging therapies for cLBP.

Read more: [Deep-learning-based biomarker of spinal cartilage endplate health using ultra-short echo time magnetic resonance imaging](#)

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Deep-learning-based biomarker of spinal cartilage endplate health using ultra-short echo time magnetic resonance imaging

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GREI data reuse story
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Key research information:

- The goal of this study was to use imaging biomarkers of disc biochemical composition to distinguish degenerative changes associated with chronic lower back pain from normal aging
- Data from 133 participants indicate that the effects of aging on the biochemical composition of discs in the lower back may involve a relatively uniform set of factors from which many patients with chronic lower back pain deviate.

Read more: [ISSLS Prize in Bioengineering Science 2023: Age- and sex-related differences in lumbar intervertebral disc degeneration between patients with chronic low back pain and asymptomatic controls in *European Spine Journal*](#)

Current status: Research team has uploaded multiple data packages for all three studies to the Vivli platform.

Key user feedback:

- “The submission checklist through NIH HEAL and a tutorial video was incredibly helpful, especially in understanding how Vivli links data to the HEAL Data Platform.”
- “The dashboard lets researchers clearly see uploaded studies, submissions, data packages, and study documents. Everything feels well organized.”
- “Data package requirements are clear: once all four required elements—protocol, IPD, data dictionary, and SAP—are in place, work can proceed.”

Key user feedback:

- “Uploading the data packages was challenging because the team has many files and publications for each study. It would be helpful if related files could be bundled together by publication rather than appearing as a long list under one study.”
- “It would be helpful to have guidance on how to organize data package files covered under multiple publications before uploading the data package onto the platform.”
- “There was some confusion about aspects of the submission process—who should sign forms, agreements, and approvals, and in what order.”

⇒ **Opportunities to improve user experience**